

CHARACTERIZATION OF DRIVING MECHANISMS INVOLVED IN DECONSOLIDATION OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE LAMINATES

Luc Amedewovo, Arthur Levy, Laurent Orgeas, Basile de
Parscau du Plessix, Steven Le Corre

arthur.levy@univ-nantes.fr

Today's challenges

Increase part complexity

Pylone MATCH project

Boeing assembly line

- Intricate / thick parts
- Large parts
- Assembly

Cheap / sustainable

www.sabca.be

- Fast and efficient cycles
- Out-of-autoclave
- Defect free

TP composites

TPC manufacturing steps

structure

Post processing

Heat
No/low pressure

Prepregging

Litzler

Consolidation

Conformation

stamping

Layup

nip point

Assembling

overmoulding

welding

Deconsolidation

Welding

GF/PEI resistance welding

[Shi et al. 15]

Thermo stamping

[Donnadei et al. 18]

State of the art hypothesis

Moisture

[Slange et al. 18]

Thermo-mechanics

[Donadei et al 18]

Motivation

Understand the deconsolidation phenomenon,
need for characterization

Outlines

1 - Material

2 - Microstructural in-situ analysis

3 - Macroscopic parametric study

Laminate preparation

Material

CF/PEKK (Toray Composites)
348 * 348 mm*2,90 mm
16 plies UD, 0°

Consolidation

- Press (40 bar)
- Oven (VBO)

Pre-conditionning

- Drying 180°C / 72h
- Ambient storage
(for 5 months → 0.013 % H₂O)

courbe désorption sur des plaques de 80mm*80mm*16plis
stock atm.amb@5 mois

1 - Material

2 - Microstructural in-situ analysis

3 - Macroscopic parametric study

In situ Tomography Observation

Characteristics

Temperature: **450°C**

Heating rate: **2°C/min**

Pressure: **1.2 MPa**

Sample diameter: **20 mm**

Slip ring

Pneumatic actuator

Thermal insulator

310 mm

Support

150

Insulation

Sample

Confining tube
(Aluminum)

Test Matrix

#	Preconditioning	Stacking sequence	Heating type	Counter pressure
1	Water immersed (WI) 3 months @ 0.1 wt. %H2O	UD	Bi-lateral	-
2	Dried – 72h@180°C	UD	Bi-lateral	-
3	WI	CP	Bi-lateral	0.1 MPa
4	WI	UD	Uni-lateral	0.05 MPa

3D fields

- Test 2: Dried / UD / Bi-lateral

3D grey level image

Processing

Porosity content

Gray scale image

Trainable weka
segmentation
algorithm

Binary image

Global strain

$$\ln\left(\frac{\text{current thickness}}{\text{initial thickness}}\right)$$

Strain and porosity

- Test 2: Dried / UD / Bi-lateral

Processing

- **Pore size**

1. Pore fitting with Oriented Bounding Box (OBB)

pore length = a

2. Pore classification by length

3. **Volume fraction** = $\frac{\text{Pore class volume}}{\text{Total pore volume}} \times 100$

- Length ≤ 0.1 mm
- $0.1 < \text{Length} \leq 1$ mm
- Length > 1 mm

Pore growth and splitting

Test 2: Dried / UD / Bi-lateral

- Length ≤ 0.1 mm
- $0.1 < \text{Length} \leq 1$ mm
- Length > 1 mm

During deconsolidation

1 - Material

2 - Microstructural in-situ analysis

3 - Macroscopic parametric study

CODEC bench

Continuous in-
situ COMposite
DEConsolidation

[Amedewovo et al. 23]

CODEC bench

Up to 450°C
Up to 10 bars
Up to 60°C/min

Test matrix

Initial laminate		Deconsolidation	
Process	Conditionning	Counterpressure	Heating rate
HP VB	Dried Ambiant storage Immersed	No pressure 1 bar 3 bar 5 bar	5° C/min 10° C/min 60° C/min

Results

Press consolidated, Dried, no pressure, 10°C/min

Deconsolidation graph

Press consolidated,
Dried,
No pressure,
10°C/min

Max deconsolidation strain

DTS ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)

Deconsolidation critical temperature T_D

(2) Critical deconsolidation

(1) Thermal expansion

(3) Shrinkage

Maximum deconsolidation strain

Heating rate = 10°C/min

No counter pressure

%H₂O x 20

Same initial residual stress state

Relaxation of residual stresses

After experiments micrographs

UD- HP - Dried (DS) 1 week@180°C

UD - HP - Annealed (AN) 48h@250°C

**UD - HP - Annealed (AN) 48h@250°C +
Rehumidifying 1 week @ 0.04 wt. %H₂O**

Acknowledgement

- PERFORM project led by IRT Jules Verne
- PERFORM partners Airbus, Safran, Latecoere, Stelia Aerospace, Clayens NP, Naval Group and Faurecia.
- Arnaud Arrivé and Julien Aubril : CODEC bench development and fabrication
- Nicolas Lefevre for the Synchrotron bench development
- AFM for co-funding my travel

CHARACTERIZATION OF DRIVING MECHANISMS INVOLVED IN DECONSOLIDATION OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE LAMINATES

Luc Amedewovo, Arthur Levy, Laurent Orgeas, Basile de
Parscau du Plessix, Steven Le Corre

arthur.levy@univ-nantes.fr